
Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts: seven tractors: four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage: Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Heritability estimates of rice crosses

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Heritability estimates of nine quantitative characters were made using a half-diallel cross involving seven parents: Sel. ADT 27, Kataktara, ADT27, Padma, IR8, TN1, and NC1626. The formula used was: $(\frac{1}{2}\hat{D} + \frac{1}{2}\hat{H}_1 - \frac{1}{2}\hat{H}_2 - \frac{1}{2}\hat{F})$; $(\frac{1}{2}\hat{D} + \frac{1}{2}\hat{H}_1 - \frac{1}{2}\hat{H}_2 - \frac{1}{2}\hat{F} + \hat{E})$.

The estimates show that the major part of the total phenotypic variation for plant height, grain-weight, length, and breadth is due to additive genetic effects (see table). Low estimates for effective tillers, ear length, duration, grain yield, and grain number indicate the influence of nonadditive gene action in the expression of these characters.

Significant epistatic effects were detected when genetic components were analyzed for duration in crosses involving Sel. ADT27 or ADT27 as one parent. By eliminating the arrays of crosses of these two parents, the narrow sense

Estimates of narrow-sense heritability of 9 characters in rice crosses at Chinsurah Rice Research Station, West Bengal, India.

Character	Narrow-sense heritability (%)
Plant height	51.4
Effective tillers	25.6
Ear length	24.6
Duration	28.4
Grain yield	38.4
Grain number	19.8
Grain weight	76.4
Grain length	86.6
Grain breadth	61.0

heritability was 78.4%, against 28.4% in the presence of epistasis. This shows that nonadditive gene action with epistasis distorts the heritability estimate.

Selection for characters such as plant height and grain weight may be done in the early generation. Selection for characters with low heritability, such as effective tillers, ear length, duration, grain yield, and grain number, should be deferred till plants reach homozygosity. ■

Improved rice variety released in the Philippines

International Rice Research Institute

The Philippine Seed Board approved the release of IR56 on 10 June 1982. IR56 was the selection IR13429-105-2-2-1 from the cross IR4432-53-3-3/Ptb 331//IR36 made in 1976.

IR56 had superior performance in lowland cooperative trials during 1980 and 1981. Its yield potential is comparable to that of IR36; it matures in 105 days, 2-3 days earlier than IR36; it has long, slender, translucent grains with high amylose and low gelatinization temperature, and high milling recovery.

IR56 is resistant to all major diseases and insects: blast, bacterial blight, tungro, grassy stunt, green leafhopper, and three biotypes of brown planthop-

per. Its resistance to tungro is higher than that of IR36. In field trials in Mindanao, IR56 showed tolerance for ragged stunt virus. Its gene for resistance to brown planthopper and green leafhopper are different from those of IR36, thus diversifying the genetic base of improved materials being grown in Asia. ■

Three new rice varieties for Nepal

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Through collaborative testing by the International Rice Testing Program and the national rice improvement program,